

EXERGY STRATEGIES FOR THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY: DISMANTLING, DISASSEMBLY, ECO-DESIGN AND RECYCLING IN ELECTRIC VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on analyzing the recyclability capacity of the Connected Electric Vehicle (CEV) model CUPRA Born concerning different disassembly levels. Its purpose is to promote sustainable practices that efficiently and safely contribute to the supply of critical metals in the CEV's industrial value chain. For this purpose, four fundamental components of the vehicle have been examined: the permanent magnet electric engine, the charge regulator, the inverter, and the converter. Regarding the methodology applied, the starting point of this study is to manually disassemble the most critical parts in terms of mineral capital. For the recyclability analysis, three different scenarios have been considered, evaluating metal recovery in terms of mass and mineral capital. The first scenario entails the shredding of parts alongside the vehicle, exclusively recovering the ferrous fraction through the post-shredding processes applied. The second recycling scenario involves extracting parts from the vehicle and recycling them separately, following a metallurgical process aimed at copper or steel recovery. In the latter case, not only copper is recovered, but also other critical and precious metals such as gold. The final recycling scenario considered includes the disassembly of parts, their categorization into various material types, and the recycling of each subpart through the most appropriate industrial route. The composition results reveal that, overall, the analyzed parts are mainly composed of copper, iron, and aluminum, being the latter the most critical in terms of both mass and mineral capital. Additionally, other elements such as gold, platinum group metals (PGMs), and the rare earth metals have been identified in minor quantities but with a high mineral capital value because of their Thermodynamic Rarity. As an example, the charger is mainly composed in terms of mass by Al (63%), Fe (16%) and Cu (10%). As for the mineral capital, the most critical metals are: Al (77%), Au (8%) and Cu (6%). Based on the recyclability results obtained, it was noted that the disassembly significantly increases the mineral capital recovery for the parts as a whole, from 47 % to 75 %. However, a potential challenge was identified in the significant amount of aluminum present in the parts since it is not possible to efficiently recover this metal with the proposed metallurgical routes.

Keywords: Circular economy; Disassemblability; Critical raw materials; Electric vehicle (EV); Exergy analysis; Thermodynamic rarity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is experiencing a significant energy transition towards more sustainable practices, driving an increase in demand for raw materials and metals (Wells, 2013). Over the last three decades, global vehicle sales have doubled significantly (OICA, 2016). In particular, in the EU in particular, the passenger car fleet grew by 15.9 % from 2012 to 2021 (European Automobile Manufacturers' Association, 2023), and further growth is expected (The International Council on Clean

Transportation, 2021). This vehicle fleet expansion inevitably intensifies the need for raw materials in manufacturing processes (Hernandez et al., 2017).

Over the last few years, there has been a remarkable change in the amount, as well as in the types of raw materials which are essential for the production of vehicles (Ortego, Valero, Valero, & Restrepo, 2017). For instance, the manufacturing of electric powertrains relies on rare earth-based permanent magnets (Ortego, Valero, Valero, & Restrepo, 2017), whereas metals such as lithium, cobalt, nickel and manganese are integral to battery production (Simon et al., 2015). In addition, semiconductors play a crucial role in the manufacture electronic components (Andersson et al., 2016). However, most of these metals are considered critical because of supply risk issues and their growing significance in economic development (Achzet & Helbig, 2013; Alonso et al., 2007; European Commission, 2023). Supply risks associated with certain materials pose a significant threat to the automotive sector, especially with the widespread adoption of fully electric vehicles heavily reliant on critical metals.

Considering end-of-life vehicle (ELV) recycling processes, the emphasis is often on isolating harmful content, selling spare parts and recovering regulated components such as batteries, tires or catalytic converters (Andersson et al., 2016). However, current recycling processes are not addressing most of the metals contained in vehicles (Ortego, Valero, Valero, & Restrepo, 2017). Consequently, a considerable portion of alloy elements is lost through downcycling or ending up in automobile shredder residue (ASR), eventually destined for landfills (Ohno et al., 2015). Research has shown that approximately 25% of the mineral capital of an ELV is lost due to downcycling, a process where the resulting product holds lower value than the original item (Ortego et al., 2018). Metal downcycling in ELV processes remains an urgent preoccupation addressed in previous studies, (Nickel Institute, 2016),(Maurice et al., 2017). A circular and sustainable approach to improve the recycling of critical raw materials involves dismantling automotive parts containing these metals and subsequently applying specific recycling processes based on metallurgical operations (Iglesias-Émbil et al., 2023). Based on this approach, numerous innovative methodologies have been explored.

From the perspective of disassembly methodologies, Parsa et al. (Parsa & Saadat, 2021) investigated a disassembly method focused on human-robot collaboration, efficiently combining human flexibility with automated repeatability and precision. on the other hand, Liu et al, (Liu et al., 2022) proposed a new strategy to improve the disassembly of smartphones in order to minimize as much as possible the generation of waste by studying different models of smartphones and proposing optimization techniques applied to the disassembly of large fractions of these devices. After analyzing the consequences of the energy transition in other industrial sectors, it has been observed that the automotive sector is not exempt from suffering the same fate, which is why this study analyzes the recycling of the parts of an electric vehicle from the point of view of disassembly. For this purpose, it is necessary to identify and overcome the possible barriers that impede the objectives of the circular economy.

Current vehicle recycling practices mainly focus on the mass recovery of materials. At the end of their life cycle, vehicles are sent to authorized treatment facilities (ATFs) and shredder plants where processes are applied to decontaminate vehicles, reuse components, and primarily recycle ferrous and non-ferrous scrap metals. However, these processes are not efficient in recovering components and metals present in smaller yet valuable quantities. To prevent these metals from being downcycled into steel or aluminum alloys (Ohno et al., 2015), a physical parameter called Thermodynamic Rarity, defined by Valero and his team (Valero et al., 2012), has been introduced. This parameter is a universal and stable unit of measurement, reflecting the physical criticality of mineral resources, which is based on the second law of thermodynamics, with a particular focus on the concept of exergy. This concept aims to assess the mineral capital of the metals composing the study parts. This criterion has been proposed as an alternative to mass for the evaluation of materials, because it assigns a higher value to those substances which are more valuable from a physical point of view (*i.e.*, they are scarce or require important amounts of energy to be obtained). Mathematically, the Thermodynamic Rarity of a substance is obtained from the sum of the embodied exergy and the exergy replacement cost. The former is the exergy required to refine the metal coming from the mines to its final concentration and is obtained

from literature. The exergy cost of replacement is defined as the exergy required to concentrate an ore from maximum dispersion (a state of depleted Earth, known as Thanatia) to the current concentration in mines using the best available technology (Valero, 2014). The replacement exergy cost can be considered a "bonus" provided by nature, as it implies the availability of minerals concentrated in mines rather than dispersed in the earth's crust. More details on how Thermodynamic Rarity can be calculated, in relation to concentration exergy, can be found in (Ortego, Valero, Valero, & Iglesias, 2017).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Metallurgical Processes for Recycling

Vehicle parts containing the most critical and/or strategic metals have been identified as the main scope for material recovery, using the thermodynamic property mentioned above and the Material Information System Sheets (MISS) database provided by SEAT. The characterization of the critical metals through the MISS Sheets allows to know precisely the composition of the components of the electric vehicles, and therefore, the subsequent design of the metallurgical processes necessary to efficiently recover as much material as possible. These recycling processes are mainly based on the metallurgical compatibilities between the different metals, according to the recycling routes used at industrial level (Figure 1). This representation shows the final destination and consequently the recovery or loss of various materials in a product/component for different interconnected metallurgical processes.

Figure 1: Metal wheel for recycling elements according to different metallurgical processes (Schaik & van Reuter, 2013)

It should be noted the degree of recyclability or recovery of each metal will depend on the chemical compound in which it is contained. Therefore, in order to analyze the metal recyclability, it is not only necessary to know the quantity of metals in a piece, but also the chemical compounds in which these metals are contained. According to the material composition of the parts, the metallurgical recycling routes of steel and copper have been used for the recovery of ferrous and non-ferrous metals respectively. To calculate the recycling rates of each of the metals making up the car parts according to the selected route, thermochemical simulation models designed with the HSC Sim 10.0 software developed by Metso were used. For each of the material fractions, a total circularity approach has been taken into account; that is, the quality of the materials is sufficiently high so they can be applied in the same product CE (Conformite Europeene; A European standard of safety) closed loop. The metallurgical processes taking place in each of them are explained below.

- **Metallurgical route for copper recovery:** In the copper processing route, the following metallurgical processes have been carried out: oxidative copper smelting where the metallurgy is determined by the O_2 partial pressure and temperature in the reactor, lead ingot reduction and

copper refining. Oxidative lixiviation of raw copper also takes place and afterwards copper is obtained by electrometallurgical methods (Antoinette van Schaik & Markus A. Reuter, 2022).

- **Metallurgical route for steel recovery:** In the steel processing route, steel scrap smelting has been performed to produce an iron-rich, but highly contaminated alloy, as it contains some elements detrimental to steel alloy. The slag produced during steel processing will contain Al_2O_3 , BaO , CaO , SiO_2 , etc. These fractions could be applied in open-circuit CE PGMs could make alloy processing cost-effective, but generate significant residues during hydrometallurgical processing (Antoinette van Schaik & Markus A. Reuter, 2022).
- **Metallurgical route for aluminum recovery:** The remelting process for Al recycling was simulated by Paz and his team (Paz et al., 2024) using HSC Chemistry 10 software and FactSageTM version 8.2 with the following phases: (Fact PS) for the gas phase, (FToxid) for the slag, (FT salt) for inorganic salts, and the Al-based molten metal phase (FTlite) for the thermodynamic simulation of Al recovery.

2.2 Methodology Description

After defining the concepts of Thermodynamic Rarity and metallurgical compatibility, the methodology employed to do this activity was developed. This method has been structured as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Diagram of the steps to follow in the methodology used in the project

The input information consists of a database provided by SEAT known as MISS. This information contains the composition for each of the parts disaggregated by levels, in which a series of subcomponents, elements and compounds are listed. The mass balance of each piece was also checked to identify possible deviations in the data. Then, the easily disassembled sub-pieces were identified, regardless of their composition. Once the total mass of the elements contained in each of the parts were known, we proceeded to evaluate the criticality of material resources from a thermodynamic point of view, as well as the metals with the highest level of criticality. For this purpose, Thermodynamic Rarity was used. The mineral capital of each part or sub-part was calculated using equation 1.

$$Rarity = \sum_{i=1}^n m(i) \cdot Rarity(i) \quad (1)$$

In which $m(i)$ is the mass of each chemical element that constitutes the piece and $Rarity(i)$ is the Thermodynamic Rarity associated with each one of them. As was mentioned in the Introduction, Thermodynamic Rarity assesses the exergy spent to obtain a mineral from the depleted state to the mine concentration, and from there to final product concentration. The recyclability of each part was then analyzed using the following cases (Figure 3):

- **Case 1 ("shredding").** The part is shredded with the car and only the ferrous scrap (steel) is recovered from it through the magnetic processes applied in the post-shredding process, which are ineffective for the recovery of minor but critical metals.

- Case 2 (dismantling of the car). In this case, the part is dismantled from the vehicle and is taken to a specific metallurgical process depending on its composition.
- Case 3 (disassembly). In this case, the part is disassembled to have a subcomponent fraction recycled by the copper route, the aluminum route and the other one by the steel route. Finally, the quantification of the loss of mineral capital in each case is shown in section 3.3.

Figure 3: Diagram summarizing the scenarios contemplated in this activity

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Elemental composition of vehicle parts

Using the information provided by the MISS Tables, the amount and percentage of the different elements contained in each of the analyzed pieces was determined. Figure 4 shows the mass distribution (above) and the distribution of mineral capital measured by thermodynamic rarity (below) of the elements composing the vehicle's parts.

Figure 4. Mass and mineral capital distribution measured by Thermodynamic Rarity of elements composing the car parts. 4a), 4e) converter; 4b), 4f) inverter; 4c), 4g) engine; 4d), 4h) charger

As can be seen in Figure 4, for all pieces except the engine (it is composed of 61 % of iron) more than 51% of the metal mass of the piece is aluminum. Adding copper, iron and silicon to this metal, more than 96% of the mass of metals and semi-metals is obtained. On the other hand, more than 62% of the mineral capital of the pieces is aluminum. Analyzing the mineral capital of the DC/DC converter (Figure 4b), aluminum is the most important mineral, concentrating almost 88%, followed by copper. Iron loses importance, due to its low Thermodynamic Rarity, and other elements become considerable, such as Pd, Sn and Au. As in the DC/DC converter case, most of the inverter mass (Figure 4c) is composed of Al, Cu, Fe and Si, while other elements present in more than 1% by mass are Zn and Sn. For mineral capital (Figure 4d), aluminum again dominates, with more than 70% of the total, and palladium, gold and nickel exceed 1%. The permanent magnet electric engine is the only part in which the mass is concentrated in the ferrous fraction, with iron accounting for 61% of the total mass (Figure 4e), followed by aluminum and copper. Between these 3 metals, they concentrate 94% of the mass. However, analyzing the mineral capital (Figure 4f), aluminum is again the most important metal, with more than 60%. Neodymium, due to its presence in magnets, is also considerable in both mass and mineral capital, while cobalt only in terms of mineral capital. In the case of the charge regulator, aluminum is the most important metal in terms of both mass (Figure 4g) and exergy capital (Figure 4h). In mass, it is followed by iron and copper, respectively. However, in mineral capital, the second most important metal is gold, which accounts for 8% of the total mineral capital. Palladium, as in the converter and the inverter, is also important in terms of thermodynamic rarity, due to its presence in the PCBs.

As seen in the previous section, approximately 540 mg, equivalent to 355 MJ of mineral capital, are located in the charge regulator. Gold is particularly important in this part, due to the large number of PCBs that compose the piece, although it is also contained in the DC/DC converter and the inverter. In the inverter, there is just over 100 mg of gold and in the DC/DC converter 10 mg distributed mainly in the PCBs. In the case of silver, the mass of this metal amounts to more than 3200 mg between the 4 parts, being mainly concentrated in the charge regulator (2280 mg). In mineral capital it amounts to 29 MJ, an order of magnitude less than gold. These metals are some of the scarcest in the earth's crust, which makes them of high Thermodynamic Rarity (specific). The one which is present in the largest amount is Pd, almost 50 mg among the DC/DC converter, charge regulator and inverter (there are no PGMs in the engine). In total, there are 54 mg of PGMs in the 3 parts, with a mineral capital of 153 MJ. Figure 5 shows the mass contribution (g) and mineral capital (MJ) of silver, PGMs, gold and lanthanides (rare earths) for the pieces studied.

Figure 5. Contribution in mass (g) and mineral capital (MJ) of silver, PGMs, gold and lanthanides (rare earths) for the different pieces studied

3.2 Disassemblability

This section will define the disassembly level of the different parts, as well as a possible manual disassembly option for each of them. The level of disassembly to be achieved for each part is defined by the user's final target and by the accessibility of the subpart or component in consideration. In the converter case, the objective consists of removing the PCBs, as these are where the majority of the most critical metals of the part are located. As an example, with a higher percentage than 1% of

Thermodynamic Rarity (MJ) there are: Cu (66%), Pd (8%), Au (7%), Sn (5%), Ag (5%), Nb (3%), Ru (3%), Ni (1%) and Al (1%). The heat exchanger is in this case the sub-part with the highest Thermodynamic Rarity (923 MJ compared to 96 MJ for the PCB), constituted almost entirely of Al. Figure 6 shows the different sub-pieces constituting the converter disassembled.

Figure 6: Converter disassembled

For the inverter, the objective consists of extracting the PCBs and the casings, as this is where the majority of the most critical metals of the part are located. The Thermodynamic Rarity of the PCBs in the inverter is 222 MJ and the most critical elements in this case are: Pd, Au, Cu, Al, Sn, Ag, Ni, In, Zn, Sb and Ti. The inverter casings are the highest Thermodynamic Rarity sub-parts (1,415 MJ), which are composed almost entirely of Al. In order to separate the control unit (inverter) from the permanent magnet electric engine, it is necessary to remove the screws connecting the control plate to the block. Once the screws are released, the control unit is removed by pulling it upwards (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Separating the inverter from the permanent magnet electric engine

Figure 8 shows the different sub-pieces constituting the inverter disassembled.

Figure 8: Inverter disassembled

For the permanent magnet engine, the main objective is to extract the magnets in order to study their recyclability. After analyzing the Thermodynamic Rarity of the different sub-parts that make up the permanent magnet electric engine, it has been observed that there are other critical sub-parts in addition to the magnets: housings, stator and rotor without magnets. The Thermodynamic Rarity of the engine casings is 3,015 MJ and the most critical elements in this case are: Al and Cu. The rotor also has a high Thermodynamic Rarity value (3,155 MJ). The most critical metals in this case are: Al, Fe and Cu. The magnets are located inside the four blocks made up of metal layers (non-ferromagnetic). These magnets have a Thermodynamic Rarity of 1,116 MJ. The most critical metals in the magnets are: Co, Nd and Fe. The stator is the most critical sub-part of the engine. It has the highest Thermodynamic Rarity value

(6.057 MJ). The most critical elements in this case are: Al, Cu and Fe. In order to properly handle the permanent magnet electric engine, it must be separated from the inverter beforehand. Figure 9 shows the different sub-pieces constituting the permanent magnet electric engine disassembled.

Figure 9: Permanent magnet electric engine disassembled

In the charge regulator, the objective is to extract the PCBs and the casings, as this is where the majority of the most critical metals of the part are located. The Thermodynamic Rarity of the PCBs contained in the inverter is 1,140 MJ and the most critical elements in this case are: Au, Cu, Ru, Pd, Sn, Pt, Ag, Ni, Al, Zn, Nb, Fe and Co. The charge regulator casings are the sub-parts with the highest Thermodynamic Rarity value (2,408 MJ), which are composed almost entirely of Al. In order to analyze the disassemblability of the charge regulator and subsequently characterize its material, the surface of the part was cut on a machining center. Once the cutting process was completed, the parts were cleaned of impurities and residues. Following, Figure 10 shows the different sub-pieces constituting the charger

Figure 10: Complete disassembly of the charge regulator

3.3 Recyclability

3.3.1 Recycling rates of metallurgical processes: The disassembled parts have been classified into three material fractions: ferrous, non-ferrous and aluminum. The objective of this study is to virtually determine what would be the number of metals potentially recoverable by applying advanced recycling processes. The recoverability rates of metals through the copper and steel route are specified in Figure 11. These percentages were obtained by the University of Zaragoza and the company MARAS through metallurgical process simulation using the HSC Chemistry 10 software. The recovery rate of aluminum has been obtained from the study carried out by Paz and his team (Paz et al., 2024). In order to recover approximately 68 % of the aluminum, it is necessary to apply mechanical and physical methods. The percentage recovery of aluminum considering the mechanical separation and the metallurgical process is 68 %. If only the metallurgical process is applied, 99 % would be recovered.

Figure 11: Recyclability rates of different metals through the non-ferrous process and ferrous

3.4 Case 1: Recycling of parts with vehicle steel

In the first case, the parts are not separated from the vehicle and the entire car is sent for steel recycling. The only part where considerable mass recovery is achieved is the engine. Due to the low Thermodynamic Rarity of iron, the mineral capital recovery, for this part, the converter and the charger, is less than 10%. In the inverter, the mineral capital recovered does not even reach 1% (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Recovery of parts mass and mineral capital in case 1 (recycling of steel with the vehicle)

3.5 Case 2: Recycling of complete parts (not disassembled)

The copper recycling route allows the recovery of precious metals, which, although scarce in mass within the parts, are an important source of mineral capital (see section 3.1). The simulations of the three recycling processes were applied to the 4 parts (without disassembly) and both the percentage of recovered mass and mineral capital were obtained and are shown in Figure 13. In the DC/DC converter, inverter and charge controller, aluminum is the metal with the highest mass, so the aluminum recycling route is the one that allows maximum recovery of both mass and mineral capital. Due to the relatively high presence of steel in the engine, the recycling route that allows the highest mass recovery for this part is the steel route.

Figure 13: Recyclability of parts calculated on a mass and mineral capital basis and optimal route

In the case of the engine, more than 60% mass recovery can be achieved through the steel metallurgical process. The route resulting in the highest mineral capital recovery is the aluminum route, since its high mass percentage is multiplied by its relatively high thermodynamic rarity. Because of this, the recovery in percentage terms of mineral capital is higher than that of mass, for all parts except the engine. In all parts a higher percentage of the mineral capital is recovered mainly due to the content of precious metals (especially PGMs) and aluminum. The converter is the part with the highest mineral capital recovered (60.9%) due to the high aluminum content (54% of the total part).

3.6 Case 3: Recycling of disassembled parts

After disassembling the sub-parts shown in section 3.2, the composition of each one was analyzed and its recycling by the three routes considered was simulated. For each sub-piece, the recycling route which maximized mass and mineral capital was chosen and the same was done for the non-disassembled fraction. The mineral capital recovered from each sub-part was summed according to its optimal route

and the overall recyclability of the part was obtained. The same was done for the mass. Figure 14 shows the comparison of the three recyclability stages in terms of mineral capital recovery for each of the parts and for the whole of them. As can be seen, disassembly significantly increases the mineral capital recovery for the parts as a whole, from 47 % to 75 %.

Figure 14: Comparison of mineral capital recovery between the 3 recycling stages for each part

In general, for the four parts studied, there are sub-parts that require different metallurgical recycling processes, so that disassembly increases the recoverability of mineral capital. The parts where mineral recovery increases the most between cases 2 and 3 are the inverter (41.5 % increase) and the DC/DC converter (33.5 % increase). Both parts consist of some sub-parts with significant aluminum fractions and others rich in precious metals or copper, which justifies their disassembly. The variability in mass and mineral capital recovery for each part between cases 2 and 3 is shown in Figure 15. It should be noted that the engine has the highest mineral capital of the 4 parts (13,399 MJ), which is higher than the sum of the mineral capitals in the other 3 parts. Because of this, improvements in the recyclability of this part by carrying out higher levels of disassembly have a considerable impact on the sum of all the parts.

Figure 15: Improvement in mass and mineral capital recovery with disassembly for each part comparing case 3 with case 2

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the recyclability of the CUPRA Born Connected Electric Vehicle (CEV) has been analyzed in relation to different disassembly levels. For this purpose, the composition of the parts under study has been obtained. Their material characterisation and disassembly has also been carried out. Finally, different recycling stages and metallurgical routes have been proposed in order to calculate how much mass and mineral capital is recovered from each metal.

The parts analyzed are composed, in mass terms, mainly of three metals: aluminum, iron and copper. These comprise more than 85% of the total mass of each piece. In terms of mineral capital, these three metals are also the most important. Others, such as gold, PGMs and rare earths, are contained in low mass proportion, but contribute considerable mineral capital due to their high Thermodynamic Rarity.

Once the composition of the pieces and sub-pieces was obtained, the manual disassemblability of the pieces was studied. To define the scope of the disassembly of each of the pieces, the most critical sub-pieces were considered from the point of view of mineral capital (measured by Thermodynamic Rarity).

For the recyclability analysis, three stages were considered. The first stage consists of the shredding of the parts with the vehicle, from which only the steel is recovered. The second case consists of the separation of the parts and their recycling separately, following a metallurgical process oriented to the recycling of aluminum, steel or the so-called "copper route", which allows the recovery, in addition to copper, of various critical and precious metals. Case 3 consists of disassembling the parts and recycling each sub-part by the most appropriate route. The recyclability results obtained have been calculated on two different criteria, percentage recovery in mass and in mineral capital.

The disassembly stage had a high impact on the amount of mineral capital and mass that could be recovered from each part. If the total mineral capital of the 4 parts is considered, the recovery increases from 7 % when shredding with the rest of the car (case 1) to 47 % when the parts are disassembled and recycled independently (case 2). The mineral capital recovery reaches 75 % when the parts are disassembled and the sub-parts are each directed to an optimal recycling route.

Comparing the recovery of metals in terms of mass in the three recycling stages explained above, it has been observed that the recyclability of all parts increases considerably by disassembling the part and directing each sub-part to an optimal route (case 3) except in the case of the engine which increases slightly (4 %). This is due to its high iron content and recovery through the steel route, however, its recyclability in mineral capital increases notably between cases 2 and 3. The recovery of mineral capital also increases considerably between cases 2 and 3 for the rest of the parts studied. The inverter is the part with the highest improvement in recycling (42%), followed by the DC/DC converter (34%), charge controller (31%) and finally the permanent magnet electric motor (24%).

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